

STATEMENT OF RESEARCH

My research has been directed towards an understanding of some of the economic mechanisms involved in the traditional long distance trade of Asia. The focus of study was the Persian Gulf, a commercially important area astride the greatest of all mediaeval routes, the "spice route", linking China, the Far East, and India with the Near East and Europe. When this trade was at its height, from the 5th to the 16th centuries A.D., it was handled in turn by a notable series of maritime trading cities on the northern shore of the Persian Gulf. Contemporaries considered each of them remarkable for its enormous wealth which contrasted with a barren and inhospitable environment, for the extent of its commercial contacts, and for its total dependence on trade. They were, it seems, among the most commercially developed cities on the spice route and must have played an important role in it.

These trading cities have generally been considered as shipping centres and transshipment ports where the Indian Ocean ships transferred goods to smaller vessels for western shipment. However, their location from 400 to 1000 km. from the western head of the Persian Gulf and their extraordinary wealth suggest there were other factors in their greatness. It was hoped that a detailed investigation of these cities and a determination of their economic contacts and hinterlands would shed light not only on the factors governing their location and wealth, but also on the organization and the nature of their trade.

There are a large number of historical sources available for the mediaeval trade of the Persian Gulf, and they have been studied for many years. Very few however are first hand reports, and none are primarily concerned with commerce. As a result, their incidental references to trade provide little quantitative information and only hint at the relative importance of commodities, routes, or trading areas. Indeed, the earliest primary trading documents date from the period of European domination in the 16th century.

It was decided that archaeological research, besides providing a check on the historical sources, could produce some of the quantitative commercial information the documents lacked. Techniques of statistical surface survey which had proved successful in prehistoric population studies were employed with certain modifications. These methods offered the opportunity to record the size and wealth of trading cities and their satellites as well as to measure their hinterland and economic contacts through the study of the trade goods remaining on the surface. In practice it was only possible to trace trade in non-perishable items, such as pottery, glass, stone, and occasionally precious metals. Nevertheless, since both pottery and glass were traded as much for their contents as for their intrinsic value, they probably broadly represent the patterns of trade in perishable items.

The area intensively investigated included most of southern Iran and the northern shore of the Persian Gulf, where the major trading cities were situated. On the southern shore, brief reconnaissances covered five of the nine modern states. The Gulf littoral proved particularly well suited to

this field work for it is presently an arid and underpopulated region where extensive wind erosion has exposed large quantities of archaeological material on the surface of sites.

Nevertheless, this material would have been of little significance were it not possible to determine reliably the date and the place of manufacture of archaeological finds. The essential chronological framework was provided by the current large scale excavations at Siraf, itself one of the great Gulf ports. In areas where the Siraf chronology was incomplete, it was extended by my own excavations, at Sirjan in 1970 and at Tepe Dasht-i Deh in 1970 and 1971. At the start of this study very little was known about the exact provenance of pottery and glass, with the exception of oriental imports and those pots made at the Siraf kilns. It was necessary to build up the framework from there. Kiln sites in many areas of Iran in addition to the Persian Gulf coast were located by surface reconnaissance. Even when no kiln sites were found, great care was taken to identify the technical variations which characterized each production centre. In this way a large proportion of pottery found could be reliably assigned to a place or region of manufacture.

The results of the survey and analysis proved most valuable. They confirmed the great size and importance of the maritime cities, emphasized their wealth, and indicated a remarkable extent of oriental contacts. A great deal of information emerged on the origins of long distance large scale trade during the Sassanian Period. The most remarkable Sassanian discovery was a scarcely documented maritime site which had contacts at least as far as India, and was even larger than any of its well known successors. The

Investigation of commercial contacts revealed that movement of objects over the well documented mountain passes into Persia was very limited until the 14th century. It seems that the archaeological hinterland of the great ports lay elsewhere, to some extent in Mesopotamia, but also on the distant coasts of South Arabia and East Africa where Gulf pottery is common on those sites which have been examined.

The archaeological results were not treated as an end in themselves, but were considered as part of a fundamentally historical study, providing fresh evidence, in the light of which, the historical texts could be re-examined. Particular attention was focused on identifying and determining the place of origin of perishable items of trade, a parallel line of research to the archaeological study of less perishable items.

This emphasized in a striking manner the possible significance of the archaeological links between the Gulf, East Africa, and South Arabia. For while few trade items from Europe or the central Islamic lands were in demand in India and the Orient, the products of the Indian Ocean periphery, such as pearls and horses from the Persian Gulf, frankincense and aromatics from South Arabia, and ivory from East Africa were found to be highly prized in India and the East. The commodities of the Persian Gulf alone would have been enough to promote eastern trade and capital formation, even if the western demand for spices had never existed. More than this, the archaeological evidence, the activities of merchants, and the lists of Persian Gulf exports indicate that, despite competition from Red Sea ports, the Gulf cities in their prime extended their commercial power by including among their exports products of East Africa and South Arabia.

Besides suggesting an explanation for the trading ports' locations near the sea lanes to Arabia and East Africa, this trading pattern seems to make some contribution towards understanding the great riddle of East-West trade, the means the western world employed to finance its imports from the East. A widely accepted view based on impeccable sources is that this trade was to a large extent financed by exports of western gold. The consequent gold shortage has been blamed for trade recessions and political events as disparate as the fall of the Roman Empire and the collapse of the Abbasid Caliphate. In opposition to this view, it has been noted that there is little evidence for a reduction in the actual circulation of precious metals. For this reason some scholars have doubted the gold drain theory, but none has presented a coherent alternative. My research has suggested that the clue to the controversy lay in the intermediate resource zone stretching from East Africa to the Persian Gulf which provided so many of the goods the east demanded. Since this intermediate zone was industrially and agriculturally underdeveloped, it provided a ready market for western textiles, manufactured goods, and foodstuffs which had little sale in India. Thus, in the cities of the Gulf Indian spices which had been purchased with Gulf pearls might be exchanged for western textiles. This provided the means to supply the West with oriental goods without involving gold loss. In this schema the drain of western gold was only a temporary phenomenon strictly relating to those periods when direct sailing from Iraq or Egypt to India bypassed the intermediate zone which the maritime cities of the Persian Gulf represented.

The contribution this study makes to the problem of gold drain is one illustration of the wider implications of the research. In general it is

considered that the clarification of trade mechanisms operating in as commercially advanced an area as the Persian Gulf contributes to the understanding of much broader mechanisms of exchange. The basic study of archaeological material in southern Iran has helped provide a background for any succeeding study involving Iranian material. It is hopefully an example of what could be achieved elsewhere in the Islamic world with similar work. The specific results of the archaeological surface survey have presented a body of basic data which it is hoped, even if interpretations vary, can not be overlooked in future studies. The major archaeological contribution is felt to be the pioneer application of archaeological surface techniques to specific problems in mediaeval history.